

'yan Taru (Women Cadre of the Nana Asma'u)

also known as "Women Religious Movement of the Sokoto Caliphate."

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Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Islamic Revival, Uthmaniyyah, Religious Group, Uthmaniyyah Caliphate of Sokoto

'Yan Taru is a female educational empowerment movement established by Nana Asma'u (the daughter of Shaikh Uthman ibn Fodio) in 1838 to move around the caliphate on an itinerant mission to boost Islamic religious awareness among women at their matrimonial premises. The movement was a rejoinder of Ibn Fodio's effort to educate women and limit the level of illiteracy among the feminine gender that was consistently observed in educational less-advantageous personalities before the establishment of the caliphate. His educated daughter sustained the effort that remained a Teacher, educationist, and political figure in the region who published books in Hausa and Fulbe languages to draw Islamic awareness closer to those at low levels. The effort lives longer than its founder when her sister (Maryam) extended the effort longer to equip those to have taken over and establish branches of the movement wider in other regions. Likewise, her legacy inspired some intellectual women to revive the service in the present generation of Nigeria and other regions of the World.

Date Range: 1793 CE - 1864 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).pr](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).pr)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Uthman ibn Fodio (nd). *Ihya'u Sunnah wa Ikhmadu al-Bid'ah*. Abdullahi Yassar Printing press, Kano Nigeria.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.yantaru.com/aboutus.html>

– Source 1 Description: WOMEN'S EDUCATIONAL AND CHARITABLE FOUNDATION

– Source 2 URL: <https://brainandguts.nl/2021/09/14/nana-asmau/>

– Source 2 Description: Nana Asma'u. Brain & Guts

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://sias.org/yan-taru/>

– Source 1 Description: About the Yan Taru

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Many religious groups participate in the development of religious education in Sokoto Caliphate.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: The group accepts members through their interest and educational capacity to teach other women.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Women get assigned to the movement when they grow up.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: The group assigns members by personal interest.

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: Active members could be at the age of 14 or 40.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: At 14 or 40.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Yan Taru is only restricted to the female gender.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The group assigns Muslim women alone that participate in Islamic religious worship.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Educational interest could be counted among the factors of assigning members.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Yan Taru movement recruit new members that could help in the Islamic educational empowerment of the Muslim women in the Sokoto Caliphate.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The movement got the support of the polity for the position of its founder as adviser to the government.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The movement considered apostasy crime that is punishable under the polity of the caliphate.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– I don't know

Notes: Apostates are punished by execution.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 2000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 60

Notes: Members of the group were women who carried the highest percentage of the total population in the caliphate.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group adopted Qur'an as their scripture to do their services under its directives and guidelines.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Qur'an is the written scripture adopted by the religious movement in the Sokoto Caliphate.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture is written that has rewardable oral recitation.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture was revealed to the prophet Muhammad (S.A.w) in Arabia for the application of the entire Muslims.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The scripture was revealed by Allah the high God.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Allah revealed the scripture.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Allah inspired the scripture.

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: It was Allah that inspired the scripture.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: The scripture originated from a divine being (Allah).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: The scripture originated from a divine being (Allah).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The group does not have monumental architecture.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: Monumental religious structure is absent.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not have iconography.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: There is no belief in mind-body dualism.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The movement believes in the afterlife.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The religion of the movement does not approve of reincarnation in this world.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no special treatment for the corpse of a member of the movement apart from the bath and shrowding.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifice is not allowed in the religion of the group (Islam).

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No grave goods in the religion of the group.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: The burial of the members is formally done in the Muslim cemetery.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Belief in the supernatural being is present in the religion of the movement.

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Allah is considered the only God worthy to worship.

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The structure of the high God (Allah) is not known.

The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Supreme high God is the sky deity.

The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The supreme high God does not dwell in the world.

The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The supreme high God is not attached to any monarch.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The monarch is considered a servant of the supreme High God.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The Supreme High God has no kin relation to the elites.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Actions of the supreme high God are unquestionable.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Suprem high God has control over everything

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God is not restricted to a particular domain.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God extends over the entire sampled region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God is unrestricted in the sampled region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the supreme high God is unrestricted outside the sampled region.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can see everybody everywhere.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can see person everywhere.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can see what is hidden in the mind.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God knows a person's character.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God is aware of what is to happen in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Supreme high God has knowled of everything in this world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God has causal efficacy of everything in this world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God can reward good deeds in the hereafter.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God will punish evildoers in the hereafter.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God has the power to cause everything in this world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Supreme high God exhibits positive emotion on the bounties He bestowed on His creatures.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

Notes: All the emotions of the high God are good, as negative emotions are not attributed to Him.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: Supreme high God does not have a desire for food.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Whoever worships another god apart from Allah shall dwell in Hellfire forever.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: gers. Supreme high God exhibits other features apart from the mentioned.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God communicates to the living through revelation to His messengers.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: His revelation to Messengers could be awak.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Some communications happen in a dream of the messengers.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Another kind of revelation comes in a trance.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Notes: Divine practices do not attract communication with God.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Especially Prophets and Messengers.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: High God does not communicate with the monarch unless he is among the prophets or Messengers.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: rs. Revelation remained the only means of communication between God and Humans.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits are present right from the period of every creation.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: The human spirit cannot be seen.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Human life and movement indicate its presence.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

Notes: Previously, the human spirit does not know this world.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not have the power to cause anything in this world.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not have the power to cause anything, whether directly or indirectly.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit can recall what happens in life.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not exhibit any emotion.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not communicate with the living directly, only that its presence makes life possible.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Jins and angels are other non-human natural spirits that are living.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Non-Human supernatural beings are not visible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Jinns can only be felt when they possess or attach to someone.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Some are living in the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the Non-human supernatural being is restricted to the physical affairs of humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Their knowledge is not restricted within the sampled region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Their knowledge is not restricted within the sampled region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: They know what is outside the sampled region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can never know what is hidden in the mind.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal

essence):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings know the personal essence of humans.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not know what is to happen in the future.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They might have other knowledge of this world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: High God does not give them the power to cause efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: They do not have the power to cause efficacy in the world, whether directly or indirectly.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: But are not visible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Their negative emotions are not visible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Jinns possess hunger, while angels do not possess hunger.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: But are not visible to humans.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: Mixed human-divine is not available in the religion of the group.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Religious group does not possess other supernatural being.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: God is ever monitoring the activities of humans.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Angels are attached to every human to monitor and record his deeds.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: They do not have concerns about taboos.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: They record it as a sin against the killer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: They record it as transgressions on the Islamic Shari'ah that prohibits the act.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Angels assign to humans record it against the person except under the directives of the Shari'ah.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: Angels do not have a desire for sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: They record it as a sin against the person to have done it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: They record it as a good act that would be rewarded hereafter.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Except if it leads to weakness in religious practices.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: They considered it prohibited by the high God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Notes: They do not care about shirking risk.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: They considered it prohibited.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: They record it as a sin against the person.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: They considered it prohibited and recorded it as a sin against the person.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Especially prayer and the rest of the Islamic worship acts.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They considered it a commendable act.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
 - Notes: They considered it a good act.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: The go along with the persons they were assigned to.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: They punish in the hereafter on the directives of the God.

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Only the high God metes out punishment.
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - Notes: High God assign Angels to punish infidels in the Hellfire.
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No

Notes: Punishment is reserved till hereafter.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: High God assigned angels to punish the transgressors.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Transgression on the directives of the Islamic Shari'ah.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: It is done to ensure people's obedience to the directives of Allah.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is stated to enforce recommendable norms.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is done to wipe out selfishness.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Punishment is done for reasons.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishment is done to ensure obedience to the directives of Islam.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishment is reserved for the hereafter.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group emphasized the punishment in the hereafter on the statement of the Qur'an.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The punishment is severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The punishment is beyond sensory displeasure as it happens on the entire body.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: There is no reincarnation in the religion of the group.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: The religion of the group rejected the belief in reincarnation.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Punishments in the afterlife are meted to one's sins

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Supernatural punishment is reserved for the hereafter.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Allah (S.W.T) is The only being responsible for bestowing rewards

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Mahadi is considered to deliberate humans towards the end of the world.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Notes: His exact date of coming is not specified but the circumstances and situations are stated

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: His appearance marks the end of the world and his sole purpose is to save humanity from getting doomed.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Islam prescribed the accepted norm of the religious group.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The group accepts norms prescribed by Islam alone.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No celibacy is required in joining the group.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: But sexuality must be lawful under the directives of the Islamic religion.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is not among the requirements for joining the group.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is only required in the month of Ramadan, as mandated by Islam.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Permanent scarring is not among the prerequisite of joining the group.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: The sacrifice of adults is prohibited in the religion of the group.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership does not require the sacrifice of children.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: The religion of the group prohibits suicides.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Membership is voluntary and does not require the sacrifice of properties.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Membership requires attendance at meetings, especially when going around to educate women.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: It only requires a sacrifice of time.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Membership requires acceptance of all precepts of Islam.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: They work mutually.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: No other rituals apart from the services prescribed by Islam.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: It only requires attendance to the services directed by Islam.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: The group did not employ fictive kinship terminology.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The society of the group was named Sokoto Caliphate.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: The group was only made for the educational empowerment of the Muslim women in the Sokoto caliphate.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Obligatory charity (Zakat) and voluntary donations to the group might be considered as famine relief.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: They only carry what to eat when moving around in the caliphate.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They usually receive support from the caliphate.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Showing care for the elderly and less privileged is a personal opinion and an act of kindness and compassion.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: They educate members on Islamic religious knowledge, who are then sent on itinerant missions to educate women in their homes.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group received education through the office of Nana Asma'u, who founded the group.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the groups interact with appointed teachers (Jajis) who manage the group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group interact with the bureaucracy of the Sokoto caliphate through the office of Nana Asma'u (daughter of ibn Fodio).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, however, that depends on the community in question.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: depends on the circumstances

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: They transport themselves to the communities for educational empowerment.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, as they usually move on independently.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Zakat is being collected from those members having what to give.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The caliphate levied taxes on those having the amount of Zakat.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The group is restricted to educational empowerment alone.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They sought protection from the police force when going to dangerous communities.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: They only provide women intellectuals.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Punishments are the duty of the caliphate not the group.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: They followed the shari'ah legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subjected to the legal codes of the Sokoto caliphate.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– I don't know

Notes: The group does not have an institutionalized military force.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group did not participate in any military campaign institutionalized by the caliphate.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group enjoys the military protection of the Sokoto caliphate in the course of their educational empowerment.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: They only use Arabi, Fulfulde, and Hausa as the languages writing documents.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group uses Fulfulde and Hausa languages in addition to the Arabic language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group uses Hijrah lunar calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group adopted the calendar from the Islamic timing system.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: The group uses the charity they received from people to buy what to eat in the cause of their itinerant circle.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: They might received indirect food support from the caliphate.

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General References

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